

THEORIES OF FOREIGN SCIENTISTS WHO SCIENTIFICALLY SHED LIGHT ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL PROCESSES OF EARLY ADOLESCENCE.

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ABSTRACT: In the article, foreign psychologists have scientifically proven several theories about the period of early adolescence, biogenetic theory, who have emphasized the biological determinants of development and interpreted their qualities, and highlighted them as examples.

Key words: early adolescence, theory, period, stage, biogenetic theory

Foreign psychologists have put forward several theories about early adolescence. As an example, Erikson divides the life cycle into eight stages (phases). The first stage is infancy. Its main purpose is to create a feeling of "trust" in the outside world. His main tool is the love and care of his parents. If the baby does not develop "reasonable trust", then the feeling of "reasonable mistrust" and anxiety will appear in the world. The second stage - early childhood - feelings of shame and doubt appear in the child. The child develops such qualities as independence, responsibility, respect for order and discipline. The third stage is the game Age (age 5-7) a sense of initiative, a sense of doing something appears. At this age, group games, communication with peers, and the development of imagination are important. At this age, there is a sense of justice and understanding of compliance with the rules. The fourth stage - a new psychological structure at school age - the ability to achieve goals, a sense of initiative. The fifth stage is adolescence, which is characterized by the emergence of a sense of individuality, unlike others. Erikson fully describes the mechanisms of self-awareness, a new sense of time, and the formation of sexual interests. The sixth stage - Youth - the need and ability for intimate psychological intimacy with others, including sexual intimacy, emerges. The seventh stage - in the period of maturity, the feeling of productivity in all spheres of life activity (in work, creativity, care, leaving flowers, transfer of experience, etc.) is a constant companion and acts as a motivation for the realization of good intentions. In his theory, the scientist expressed his opinion about the specific characteristics of each era and proved his theories. Another Russian psychologist L. S. Vygotsky

noted that there are many theories about early adolescents as early as the 1920s. 3 major trends can be distinguished about the first teenagers. The first direction is called the biogenetic direction, which is based on the biological processes of maturation. The second direction is called the sociogenetic direction, in which the main focus is on socialization. The third direction is called psychogenetic, and it is based on the development of mental processes and functions. In biogenetic theories of development, the main emphasis is placed on the biological determinants of development. The development process itself is interpreted as maturation, the stages of which are universal. An American psychologist of the 20th century is one of the bright manifestations of this direction

It is S. Hall. He stated that the main law of developmental psychology is the biogenetic "law of recapitulation", according to which individual development, ontogeny repeats the main stages of phylogeny. Infancy repeats the animal phases of development. Childhood corresponds to the period when the main occupations of ancient people were hunting and fishing. The period from 8 to 12 years is called pre-adolescence, the end of wildness and the beginning of civilization. From 12-13 years to 22-25 years is called adolescence, the beginning of adulthood, the period of romanticism. . During this period, external and internal conflicts escalate, and a "sense of individuality" appears in a person. This theory is criticized by psychologists. Another version of the biogenetic theory was developed by representatives of the German "constitutional psychology". E. Krechmer and E. Jensch developed problems of personality typologies on the basis of some biological factors (types of body structure, etc.) and assumed that there must be some connection between the physical types of a person and his developmental characteristics. E. Krechmer all people can be placed on two sides, on one side cycloid (easily agitated, changeable mood) and on the other side schizoid (poor, lack of bright emotions) types can be placed. K. Konrad, Krechmer's student, said that these descriptions can be applied to age stages as well: preadolescence corresponds to the "cycloid" period, and early adolescence corresponds to the "schizoid" period. Adolescence of a schizoid person is complicated and difficult, his feelings are deepened by individual-typological characteristics.

The German scientist W. Seller in his work "Constitution and Development" (1952) stated that the connecting link between mental and somatic development is the change of the child's body structure and its awareness.

Manifestations of the biogenetic direction have focused scientists' attention on the study of mental and physical interdependence of development. This was of great importance for psychophysiology. Understanding the development of the psyche only on the basis of biological laws has not been successful. They want to eliminate the role of social factors of development and exaggerate only the role of biological factors. Transition to a new stage of development will be possible based on the resolution of the main contradiction inherent in the previous stage. If the conflict is not resolved, it will certainly appear later.

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